

Systematic Mapping Study Protocol

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A structured review protocol was defined prior to data collection, following the recommendations of [Kitchenham e Charters 2007] and [Petersen et al. 2015]. The protocol specified: Research questions; Search strategy; Selection criteria; Screening procedures; Data extraction fields; and Classification framework. Establishing the protocol in advance aimed to minimize researcher bias, prevent scope drift during screening, and ensure the reproducibility of the mapping process.

The systematic mapping covered studies published between January 2019 and May 2024. This time frame was established as the cut-off period in the review protocol to maintain methodological consistency and avoid iterative expansion of the dataset during analysis. As emphasized by [Kitchenham e Charters 2007] and [Petersen et al. 2015], systematic studies necessarily rely on clearly defined temporal boundaries to preserve internal validity and replicability. Although AI ethics research continues to evolve rapidly, the selected period captures a recent and representative snapshot of lifecycle-oriented artifacts emerging in response to contemporary technological and regulatory developments.

1. Research Questions

According to [Kitchenham e Charters 2007], specifying the research questions is the principal part of any SMS. As the research goal is to map solutions to address ethics in the development of AI systems, the main research question (RQ), aligned with the aforementioned goal, is: *What solutions are available to support developers and designers in reflecting on and applying ethical principles in AI software systems?*

To address this RQ, we defined four specific questions (SQ) to better characterize the solutions, shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Specific Questions

Specific Question	Examples
<i>SQ1</i> What types of approaches do the solutions consist of?	<i>Notions, Procedures, Code, Infrastructure, Education, Ex-post assessment and agreement</i>
<i>SQ2</i> Which ethical principles do these solutions address?	<i>Beneficence, Non-Maleficence, Autonomy, Justice, Explicability</i>
<i>SQ3</i> At which stage(s) of the AI system lifecycle can they be applied?	<i>Business and use-case development, System design, Training and test data procurement, Building, Testing, Deployment, Monitoring</i>

2. Search Strategy

To ensure methodological transparency, the search string was constructed following the PICOC framework (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcomes, Context), as recommended by [Kitchenham e Charters 2007].

The PICOC elements were operationalized as follows: Population (P) - AI systems and their development processes; Intervention (I) - Ethical artifacts, tools, frameworks, methods, and practices; Comparison (C) - Not applicable, as the study aims at mapping and classification rather than comparative evaluation [Petersen et al. 2015]; Outcomes (O): Operationalization of ethical principles in development activities; Context (C): Artificial Intelligence and the AI system lifecycle.

Based on these PICOC elements, the search string was structured to combine terms related to AI, ethics, and development-oriented practices. Particular care was taken to avoid excessive restriction to traditional Software Engineering terminology, since relevant contributions may emerge from Human–Computer Interaction, responsible AI, or interdisciplinary venues.

The string construction followed a multi-step validation process: (i) Initial derivation based on prior secondary study [Morley et al. 2020]; (ii) Expert consultation with HCI researchers; (iii) Pilot searches to assess coverage and precision; (iv) refining the terms by identifying relevant synonyms; and (v) Refinement to balance recall and specificity. The final search string was defined as:

(1) **Population:** “(software development” OR “algorithm development”) AND (2) **Intervention and Outcomes:** ethic* AND (3) **Context:** (“artificial intelligence” OR “machine learning”)

While the inclusion of development-related terms may appear closer to Software Engineering discourse, this choice reflects the study’s lifecycle-oriented perspective and its focus on artifacts that support practical ethical integration in AI system projects, rather than purely conceptual or normative discussions.

The search was conducted in the following digital libraries: **ACM Digital Library**¹, **IEEE Xplore Digital Library**², **Scopus**³, and **Springer**⁴. The combination of these databases was intended to minimize disciplinary bias and ensure coverage of both technical and design-oriented research communities. In particular, ACM Digital Library was included to capture contributions emerging from the HCI community, which may frame ethical concerns in terms of design, interaction, or user-centered approaches rather than strictly software engineering terminology.

The selection of digital libraries was guided by the objective of ensuring comprehensive coverage across the research venues in Artificial Intelligence, Human–Computer Interaction, and Software Engineering. In line with recommendations for systematic studies in computing research [Kitchenham e Charters 2007, Petersen et al. 2015], databases were chosen based on their indexing breadth, disciplinary coverage, and relevance to

¹<https://dl.acm.org/>

²<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org>

³<http://scopus.com>

⁴<https://link.springer.com/>

peer-reviewed scientific publications.

Additionally, we included **arXiv**⁵, which compiles articles from the *gray literature* and stands out for its fast publication process compared to peer-reviewed journals. This choice is particularly relevant given the emerging, rapidly evolving nature of the research topic, which allows access to recent and innovative studies.

The Brazilian Computer Society Open Library (SOL/SBC) was not queried as an independent source. Its proceedings are partially indexed in international databases such as Scopus and ACM Digital Library, which were included in this study. Following established guidelines for systematic mapping studies [Kitchenham e Charters 2007, Petersen et al. 2015], priority was given to multidisciplinary databases with broader international coverage and advanced search capabilities to ensure replicability and consistency of the search process.

Once the repositories were defined, it was necessary to establish the criteria for evaluating the quality of the results returned by the search string. As suggested by [Kitchenham et al. 2009, de Fátima Granatto et al. 2016, Barbosa et al. 2021] in previous Systematic Review Studies, the criteria used to accept the search string were (1) the volume of articles related to the topic returned in the first two pages of results and (2) the return of two articles relevant to the SMS in the first page of results. The two articles considered relevant to the proposed SMS are:

- Barbosa, S. D. J., Barbosa, G. D. J., Souza, C. S. D., & Leitão, C. F. (2021, March). A semiotics-based epistemic tool to reason about ethical issues in digital technology design and development. In Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (pp. 363-374).
- Shneiderman, B. (2020). Bridging the gap between ethics and practice: guidelines for reliable, safe, and trustworthy human-centered AI systems. *ACM Transactions on Interactive Intelligent Systems (TiiS)*, 10(4), 1-31.

3. Selection Criteria

Specific selection criteria were established to evaluate primary studies retrieved from publication databases, applied across three selection rounds. We had only one criterion for including a study in our mapping: The publication presents an approach that developers, engineers, and designers can practically apply to help them reflect on and incorporate ethical considerations into the development of AI systems.

On the other hand, we had several criteria (EC) for excluding a study from our SMS, i.e., a study was excluded if it met at least one of the following criteria:

- EC1: The publication is not explicitly related to the objective/scope of this study.
- EC2: The publication is not a scientific article or book chapter but rather a book, tutorial, editorial, abstract, poster, panel, lecture, roundtable, workshop, demonstration, preface, etc.
- EC3: The study is a duplicate, or a more recent or comprehensive version of the same research exists.
- EC4: The study compiles results from other studies.

⁵<https://arxiv.org/>

EC5: The study is not written in English or Portuguese.

EC6: The full text of the study is not available.

In contrast to systematic literature reviews aimed at synthesizing empirical evidence or comparing intervention effectiveness, systematic mapping studies prioritize breadth of coverage and structural classification of research contributions [Petersen et al. 2015]. Since the objective of this study is exploratory - focusing on identifying, categorizing, and mapping artifacts across ethical principles and lifecycle stages - no formal methodological quality assessment of primary studies was conducted.

4. Screening Procedure

The papers went through the following three-step filtering process, with the selection criteria applied in each of steps:

- **Preliminary reading (1st filter):** In the first round, the title, abstract, and keywords of the set of publications returned in the search engines were inspected according to the established inclusion and exclusion criteria and unrelated documents were removed. In case of disagreement and doubts about any of the publications, these were maintained for the next step of the selection process.
- **Diagonal reading (2nd filter):** In the second round, only the introduction, main topics, and conclusions of the selected publications from the first round were read to analyze whether they were associated with the research questions. Here, the inclusion and exclusion criteria established for the research were also applied, by which those considered irrelevant were removed. In case of doubt regarding the removal of a paper, it remained on the list and was analyzed in the next step.
- **Complete reading (3rd filter):** In the final round of filtering, a complete reading of the remaining papers was carried out, with the finally selected papers included in the data extraction process.

5. Data Extraction

The data extraction process of selected papers was systematically conducted using MS Excel to ensure accuracy and organization. A sheet was created to register the information from each paper to answer the SQs. The fields of the extraction sheet are described in Table 2.

Table 2. Data Extraction Form

No.	Description
1	Demographic data (Title Year, Authors, Authors' affiliation, Country, Venue, Publication Type, Database)
2	What type of approach does the solution consist of? (SQ1)
3	What are the ethical principles addressed by the solution? (SQ2)
4	What ethical issues does the solution seek to mitigate? (SQ3)
5	At which stage(s) of the AI system lifecycle can the solution be applied? (SQ4)

6. Classification and Synthesis

During data analysis, the identified solutions were classified using four complementary frameworks: the categories of **ethical AI approaches** proposed by [Prem 2023], the five **ethical principles** defined by [Floridi et al. 2018], and the **stages of the algorithmic development lifecycle** outlined by [Morley et al. 2020].

Data synthesis followed a descriptive mapping approach consistent with the objectives of systematic mapping studies [Petersen et al. 2015]. Frequencies of artifacts per approach, ethical principle and issue, and lifecycle stage were computed to identify distribution patterns, concentration trends, and potential gaps. Given the exploratory and classificatory nature of this study, no meta-analytic statistical synthesis was conducted.

References

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